

1 **How natural infection by *Nosema ceranae* causes honeybee colony collapse**

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19 **Summary**

20 In recent years, honeybees (*Apis mellifera*) have been strangely disappearing from their
21 hives, and strong colonies have suddenly become weak and died. The precise aetiology
22 underlying the disappearance of the bees remains a mystery. However, during the same
23 period, *Nosema ceranae*, a microsporidium of the Asian bee *Apis cerana*, seems to have
24 colonized *A. mellifera*, and it's now frequently detected all over the world in both healthy
25 and weak honeybee colonies. For first time, we show that natural *N. ceranae* infection can
26 cause the sudden collapse of bee colonies, establishing a direct correlation between *N.*
27 *ceranae* infection and the death of honeybee colonies under field conditions. Signs of
28 colony weakness were not evident until the queen could no longer replace the loss of the
29 infected bees. The long asymptomatic incubation period can explain the absence of
30 evident symptoms prior to colony collapse. Furthermore, our results demonstrate that
31 healthy colonies near to an infected one can also become infected, and that *N. ceranae*
32 infection can be controlled with a specific antibiotic, fumagillin. Moreover, the
33 administration of 120 mg of fumagillin has proven to eliminate the infection, but it cannot
34 avoid reinfection after 6 months. We provide Koch's postulates between *N. ceranae*
35 infection and a syndrome with a long incubation period involving continuous death of
36 adult bees, non-stop brood rearing by the bees and colony loss in winter or early spring
37 despite the presence of sufficient remaining pollen and honey.

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44 Introduction

45 As a bee colony can be considered as a complex living system of individuals that functions
46 as a whole, disease pathology of an individual bee is different to the pathology at the
47 colony level. Indeed, a particular pathogen can be lethal to bees but the colony may be
48 able to compensate for their loss. In this sense, the queen is essential to maintain the
49 population of the colony stable. Depopulation syndrome or honeybee colony collapse has
50 recently been the focus of many reports that have tried to determine why strong colonies
51 suddenly, or at least that's the way it seems, become weak and occasionally die (Faucon
52 et al., 2002; Higes et al., 2005; Ortiz, 2005; González, 2007; Stokstad, 2007; Molga, 2008).
53 Many colonies are lost completely without any evident signs of a disorder. Yet these
54 observations could be just the tip of the iceberg as colony breakdown may just be the final
55 phase of a long process or of chronic infection by a silent pathogen. During the same
56 period that this syndrome has been detected all over the world, *Nosema ceranae* seems
57 to have colonized *Apis mellifera* (Martín-Hernández et al., 2007), and it is now frequently
58 detected in both healthy and weak honeybee colonies (Cox-Foster et al., 2007). *Nosema*
59 *ceranae* is a widespread microsporidium that seems to have recently jumped from its
60 host, the Asian honeybee *Apis cerana*, to the worldwide honey producer, *A. mellifera*. As it
61 was first detected outside of Asia (Higes et al., 2006), its presence has been confirmed in
62 four continents, although there is no available data from Africa (Chauzat et al., 2007; Cox-
63 Foster et al., 2007; Klee et al., 2007; Martín-Hernández et al., 2007; Chen et al.,
64 2008). *Nosema ceranae* is very pathogenic when experimentally inoculated into *A. mellifera*
65 (Higes et al., 2007; Paxton et al., 2007), and natural infection has been associated with a
66 syndrome of gradual depopulation, copious colony death in autumn or winter and poor
67 honey production. In fact, the risk of colony depopulation is six times higher in colonies
68 infected with *N. ceranae* than in uninfected ones (Martín-Hernández et al., 2007). Here, we
69 show the pathological repercussion of *N. ceranae* infection of colonies and its clinical
70 evolution until the colony dies. We have not only analysed the natural infection of *N.*
71 *ceranae*, but also demonstrate the trans-mission of the disease to nearby uninfected hives
72 and the effect of fumagillin (as Fumidil B) in controlling the infection.

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74 Results and discussion

75 *Clinical monitoring*

76 Once the presence of spores from *Nosema* spp. was detected microscopically in a
77 productive honeybee colony (B255) in the experimental apiaries of CAR, the species was
78 identified as *N. ceranae* and this was confirmed throughout the study (Accession Number
79 DQ 329034). Infection was transmitted to another uninfected colony (B111) and 13
80 uninfected nuclei within 3 months, while another nucleus was infected after 5 months of
81 exposure. From the outset, it was difficult to define the health status of a colony following
82 infection as no classic signs of nosemosis were evident (OIE, 2004). As the mean spore
83 count fluctuates greatly from the start to the end of the disease in interior bees (Fig. 1A),
84 this is not a reliable measure of a colony's health when bees are infected with *N. ceranae*
85 (CATPCA analysis, Fig. S1). Indeed, *Nosema* infection cannot be assessed at the colony
86 level on the basis of bees sampled from the brood nest (El-Shemy and Pickard, 1989). In
87 fact, the proportion of forager bees infected with *N. ceranae* was the only useful indicator
88 of the extent of disease in the colony (Pearson $r = -0.8$, $P = 0.001$) and like the spore count,

89 foragers were always more infected than interior bees. The more foragers infected, the
90 smaller the number of brood combs and the fewer frames full of bees (Pearson, $P = 0.001$,
91 CATPCA, Fig. S1). This relationship did not hold for the proportion of infected interior bees
92 or the spore counts. The dynamics of bees and brood combs were related to the
93 proportion of infected foragers and the maximum mean temperatures (regression
94 stepwise: adjusted R^2 : 0.702). No statistical differences could be established with other
95 meteorological parameters. Four Phases of natural *N. ceranae* infection were determined
96 (Fig. 1A). Each of the phases of clinical nose-mosis were observed in the whole colonies
97 (number of combs = 10 or higher, if honey is going to be collected and an upper box is on
98 the brood chamber box then $n = 20$), although they were milder in the B111 hive probably
99 because of its infection in summer and not in spring. Nuclei only displayed three phases
100 probably because of the fact that the nuclei had fewer combs and consequently, a smaller
101 bee population. At the outset, infected colonies looked similar to those of other
102 uninfected hives, at least from the spring to early autumn months, without any sign of
103 disease. This was defined as Phase 1 or the ‘asymptomatic’ phase. Fewer than 60% of
104 foragers were infected ($n = 30$) and mean spore counts never rose above one million. Next
105 phase was considered as Phase 2 or the ‘replacement’ phase and started when unusual
106 colony behaviours were detected (for this region) when the queen continued to lay eggs
107 throughout the winter months (brood area around 125 cm²). The fact that this phase took
108 place in winter when the number of newborn bees is low could explain why the percentage
109 of foragers and mean spore counts were always higher than in Phase 1. The third phase
110 started the following spring when the colonies built up rapidly and the queens laid so
111 many eggs that almost every comb was full of brood. Clinical parameters (forager
112 infection, spore counts) were similar to Phase 1 and as a result of the increasing bee
113 population, this Phase 3 was named as the ‘false recovery’ phase. The bee population had
114 built up in such a way that swarming seemed imminent but it never happened. The egg-
115 laying ‘fever’ went on until the autumn when sudden depopulation (fewer than 40% of
116 frames covered with bees) was observed and the brood reached a minimum, defining the
117 fourth ‘depopulation’ phase. In this phase, the bees were very active but 2 months later,
118 the queen was found dead and surrounded by only young bees that probably died because
119 of the cold (breakdown or col-lapse, Table 1). Pollen and honey stores were present and
120 even then, a tiny brood spot of capped brood cells was detected in most colonies. Only in
121 the fourth phase were more than 40% of the interior bees infected with a much higher
122 proportion of infected foragers (like Phase 2).

123 The dynamics of the B111 and B255 colonies were very similar. Hive B111 (Fig. 1B) was
124 infected in summer and so, the first asymptomatic phase lasted for the 3 months of
125 autumn and with fewer than 50% of the foragers infected, the second phase started in
126 winter with fewer foragers infected than in hive B255 and more brood (three brood combs
127 versus 1 in B255). This delayed infection coupled with enhanced replacement could
128 explain the lower proportion of infected interior or forager bees. During the next spring and
129 early summer (about a year after infection), false recovery was evident through the
130 presence of brood in the combs of the upper box in June. However, again the colony did
131 not swarm and from this 3rd phase of false recovery, the colony displayed clear signs of
132 depopulation (Phase 4) and death was imminent. All the untreated nuclei (CN6–CN10,
133 NSN1–NSN4) had brood combs throughout the study until they collapsed (Fig. 1C) and at
134 least one comb with brood was found even during the coldest months (December–
135 February, Fig. 2A). Breakdown occurred in all the untreated nuclei (CN6–CN10, NSN1–

136 NSN4) and none of the nine nuclei wintered. Maybe because of the smaller population
137 (the nuclei had only 5 combs instead of 10), Phase 3 of false recovery was not seen and
138 from Phase 2 they went directly to Phase 4 of depopulation and death. While some died in
139 the winter, the remaining nuclei did so in the early spring, generally after a much shorter
140 incubation period than in the whole colonies and reaching the depopulation phase 3–5
141 months after infection. Like whole colonies, collapse occurred in a 2 month period and
142 again, more than 80% of the foragers (Table S1) were infected and fewer than 40% of the
143 combs (n = 5) were full of bees. Two ways of collapse were established that could be
144 related to the moment in which the colonies or nuclei died (Fig. 1C, Table 1). When
145 collapse occurred during the cold months, more than 50% of the bees found dead inside
146 the hive were infected, the mean spore count in these bees was always higher than 10
147 million, and the queens (when found) were infected. However, when collapse occurred
148 later in early spring, the percentage of infection and mean spore counts were lower.
149 Moreover, under these circumstances, the queens were usually uninfected or infection
150 could only be detected by PCR. Probably, the differences between these two cases reflect
151 the quantity of old and young bees in each season. In early spring, the proportion of
152 newborn uninfected bees will reduce the infection parameters, thereby delaying the
153 infection of the queen (Table 1).

154 Similar pathological lesions were seen in samples from dead or dying bees collected from
155 the ground of a *Lavandula latifolia* crop and in infected bees collected from hives
156 throughout the year, even in the summer months. Cells all along the ventriculus
157 epithelium were infected (Fig. 3), showing comparable alterations to those described
158 experimentally (Higes et al., 2007), and intracellular germination was also seen. Indeed,
159 there was evidence of epithelial cell degeneration and extensive lysis. The heavily infected
160 cells may either be dead or dying, which will eventually lead to the early death of the
161 infected worker bees as a result of starvation (Liu, 1984). Although pathological features
162 due to *N. ceranae* closely resembled those of *N. apis*, some clinical signs usually
163 associated with *N. apis* infection were not observed, such as crawling bees, dysentery
164 evidenced by the presence of fecal spots in the hive or supersedure of the queen. Foragers
165 collected in lavender crop were infected with a mean of 21 million *N. ceranae* spores per
166 bee. This demonstrates that some heavily infected foragers did not return to the hive. The
167 age at which worker honeybees begin foraging varies under different colony conditions
168 and the age at which foraging commences seems to be delayed in the presence of
169 foragers (Huang and Robinson, 1996). Thus, when the number of foragers is depleted, the
170 age of onset of this behaviour drops (Huang and Robinson, 1996; Amdam and Omholt,
171 2003). Infestation by *Varroa destructor* mite was recently proposed to influence the flight
172 behaviour of forager bees such that they might not return to the colony (Kralj and Fuchs,
173 2006). This effect was interpreted as an adaptative behaviour of the bees to expel the
174 pathogens from the colony, a process known as 'suicidal pathogen removal'. In a other
175 interpretation of data, the death due to *N. ceranae* could be a sudden event or a
176 debilitating process by which bees cannot return to the hive. This population must be
177 replaced by interior bees, which presumably start flying some days earlier than usual, as
178 previously associated to *N. apis* infection (Hassanein, 1953). Once the queen cannot
179 compensate for the loss of foragers, depopulation becomes evident and death is
180 forthcoming.

181 Throughout the period studied, no adult or brood dis-eases were diagnosed, no other
182 parasites were detected and Israeli acute paralysis virus (IAPV), a virus that was only

183 identified in one of the nuclei studied, was not isolated in B255 bees, (Table 2). Indeed,
184 this is the first report of IAPV in Spain. This virus was previously proposed as a CCD marker
185 (Cox-Foster et al., 2007); however, it is not prevalent in our studies and it was not
186 associated with colony collapse. The microsporidium may have some influence on other
187 viruses, as the epithelial lesions caused by the parasite reduce the natural resistance that
188 the intestinal barrier provides against viral infection. Many viruses have been associated
189 with *N. apis* infection (revised by Chen and Siede, 2007), possibly because of the
190 cytopathogenic effect that facilitates transenteric viral infection. The absence of clinical
191 signs related to viruses suggests that infection was covert or latent. Although some viruses
192 were detected by PCR in B255 and in six nuclei, B111 and four nuclei were negative and no
193 relationship could be established between the presence of these viruses and collapse
194 (Table 2). Chronic bee paralysis virus (CBPV) and deformed wing virus (DWV) viruses were
195 always detected in B255, although there were no phenotypic signs of these infections at
196 any moment. Indeed, the genomic load of the CBPV virus after colony death was about 20
197 million times lower than that necessary to produce symptoms in the nervous system
198 (Blanchard et al., 2007). Furthermore, CBPV, DWV and BQCV were also detected in
199 another six nuclei studied. While gut tissue may be a major reservoir for DWV (Chen et al.,
200 2006), virus particles were not detected in any intestinal sample studied by transmission
201 electron microscopy (TEM). The residue analysis of 40 compounds (Table S2)
202 demonstrated that the bees from all the colonies were not exposed to any pesticides. The
203 pollen availability, its diversity and the presence of more than enough stored pollen at the
204 time of breakdown (Table S3) were demonstrated by palynological studies. Moreover,
205 neither sun-flower nor corn crops, previously related with large decreases in the
206 population of bee colonies (Laurent and Rathahao, 2003), were close to the location of the
207 hive, as reflected by the complete absence of these pollens in the samples analysed
208 (Table S3). The presence of pollen is directly related with the beekeeping flora and
209 indicates the botanic resources available monthly throughout the study. Twenty different
210 taxa were found indicating high pollen diversity and availability in foraging areas. The
211 blooming period of the different taxa identified indicated that the bees had access to
212 sufficient flowers throughout the year, except in January.

213 Experiment 1: response trial in nuclei

214 In Experiment 1, fumagillin proved to be 100% effective in controlling *N. ceranae* when the
215 bee colonies are nuclei. All treated nuclei (Fig. 2B) wintered in good health and the queens
216 stopped laying eggs for 1 or 2 months. Indeed, these nuclei became colonies with 10
217 combs full of bees that developed until the next spring when they were again infected (6
218 months after treatment). By contrast, all the untreated nuclei had brood combs
219 throughout the study until they died (CN6–CN10, Fig. 2A). Breakdown occurred in all the
220 untreated nuclei (CN6–CN10, NSN1–NSN4). Furthermore, although the queen continued
221 laying eggs during the cold months, these nuclei never developed into a whole colony.
222 Significant differences were observed from November 2006 (brood combs) and December
223 2006 (bee combs). None of the treated nuclei had brood for a month or two during the cold
224 months.

225

226 Experiment 2: colony response trial

227 In the Experiment 2 (Table 3), fumagillin treatment again controlled *N. ceranae* infection in
228 standard size colonies. Treated hives were infected a year after the treatment had been
229 applied and in that moment, they were clinically in Phase 1 (Fig. S2). Fumagillin treatment
230 significantly reduced the risk of depopulation (Chi-squared, $P < 0.001$) in a 1 year period
231 and untreated colonies were always in a more advanced clinical phase or dead (Chi-
232 squared, $P < 0.001$).

233 Koch's postulates have been shown here for colonies, as previously confirmed in
234 individual bees. In essence, we have extracted the pathogen, confirmed that it can be
235 transmitted to healthy colonies inducing the disease and colony breakdown, and we have
236 recovered *N. ceranae* from these newly infected colonies. Multiplication of the parasite
237 occurs throughout the year with no standstill in its life cycle. Moreover, no differences in
238 the pathological alterations to infected bees were observed in different seasons.
239 Fumagillin treatment was a useful method to avoid colony collapse although it doesn't
240 prevent reinfection.

241 Bee biology and colony dynamics are undoubtedly influenced by multiple facts, such as
242 regional beekeeping management, health status or climate. The increasing prevalence of
243 *N. ceranae* in the last 20 years, its spread (Cox-Foster et al., 2007; Klee et al., 2007;
244 Martín-Hernández et al., 2007; Chen et al., 2008) and its capacity to cause colony
245 collapse lead us to consider it as an emergent disease. Moreover, for the first time, our
246 data provide experimental evidence of its aetiological role in the death of bees and
247 colonies under field conditions.

248

249 **Experimental procedure**

250 *Honeybee colonies*

251 The studies were performed on the experimental apiaries at the 'Centro Apícola de
252 Marchamalo' (CAR, Spain; 40°40'57.47'N, 03°12'3.08'W, Fig. 4). No genetically modified
253 agricultural crops are found in the surrounding areas, nor are insecticides such as fipronil
254 or imidacloprid used.

255 All the colonies (10 bee combs) and nuclei packages (5 bee combs) were analysed to
256 confirm the absence of any bee pathology prior to their introduction into hives at the CAR
257 apiaries. *Varroa* was controlled during the study by twice yearly treatment with amitraz
258 (Apiva®) and flumetrin (Bayvarol®), alternating the products each year. The absence of any
259 brood pathology was also confirmed.

260

261 *Experimental design*

262 i. Clinical monitoring. The first *N. ceranae*-infected colony detected was a successful and
263 productive colony named B255, previously used as a healthy control in various studies.
264 The presence of the parasite was detected microscopically on the 25 May 2005, and the
265 species was later confirmed by PCR and sequencing of the SSUrRNA gene. This colony
266 was left untreated and from the date of detection to the final death of the colony (11
267 December 2006), it was monitored monthly (about colony strength, parasitic burdens,

268 pathological studies and virological, palynological and pesticide determinations as
269 described below).

270 One year after *N. ceranae* was first detected in B255 (June 2006), 14 uninfected nuclei
271 (NSN1–NSN4; CN1–CN10) and another uninfected hive (B111) were placed close to the
272 original hive (B255). All but four nuclei (NSN1–NSN4) were checked monthly, analysing
273 samples in a similar manner to those of B255. These colonies (10 nuclei and B111 hive)
274 were used to establish differences in the evolution of the clinical signs of natural infection.
275 The remaining four nuclei were only observed visually to avoid any negative effect of
276 manipulation on bee health and behaviour.

277 Once infection was confirmed, nuclei were used in an experiment designed to determine
278 the effect of an antibiotic on the clinical evolution of nuclei through a response to
279 treatment trial (see below).

280 In summer 2006 and 2007, when the bees were foraging intensively, dead bee samples
281 were also collected from the ground from a *L. latifolia* crop situated 700 m from the
282 apiaries 1 and 2 (Fig. 4).

283 ii. Experiment 1 was carried out in 10 nuclei (CN1–CN10), five of which (CN1–CN5) were
284 treated with Fumidil B (fumagillin a.i., 1.5 g colony⁻¹ in a 250 cc syrup of
285 sugar/distilled water 50%, four treatments a week, so a total of 120 mg of fumagillin per
286 hive). Nuclei CN6–CN10 were offered the same syrup without the antibiotic (250 cc ×
287 4 applications a week), and the treatments were applied from October 2006 to November
288 2006. Syrup, with or without Fumidil B, was placed in a plastic bag over the upper surface
289 of brood combs and the entire content was consumed by the bees in fewer than 48 h. All
290 colonies were checked monthly.

291 iii. Experiment 2. The same administration regime as in Experiment 1 was used for the
292 entire 50 colonies, located in three experimental apiaries, to reproduce the real situation
293 of beekeeping under field conditions. The distance that separated the three apiaries was
294 ~500 m (Fig. 4). *Nosema* infection was diagnosed in October 2006 and 18 *N. ceranae*-
295 parasitized colonies were treated with Fumidil B in November 2006, while the other 32
296 colonies were left untreated as a control (13 *N. ceranae*-positive, 2 *N. apis*- and *N.*
297 *ceranae*-positive and 17 microsporidia-negative).

298

299 *Sample collection and determination of colony strength*

300 Throughout the study, forager and interior adult bee samples were taken monthly from
301 hives and nuclei at 12:00 at noon. Initially, the hive entrance was closed and forager bees
302 coming from the outside were taken for 30 min. Afterwards, a sample of interior bees was
303 taken. Stored pollen samples from the combs were also taken monthly from the nuclei
304 and colonies. These samples were used for multi-residue and palynological analysis in
305 order to confirm the absence of pesticides in foraged crops and the availability of pollen
306 reserves. Honey was only sampled monthly from hive B255.

307 Samples of dead adult foraging honeybees were picked up from the ground in *L. latifolia*
308 crop.

309

310 Colony strength was determined monthly by visually counting the number of combs
311 covered with bees or brood.

312

313 *Parasite determination*

314 All samples from hives and the nuclei were studied to detect the presence of Nosema
315 spores, Malpighamoeba cyst, V. destructor and Acarapis woodi mites in forager and
316 interior bees according to Office International des Epizooties methods (OIE, 2004). The
317 percentage infection and the mean N. ceranae spore burden were calculated in 30 interior
318 bees and 30 foragers analysed individually and checked each month (Doull and Cellier,
319 1961; Pickard and El-Shemy, 1989). After dissecting the bees, the gut was placed in a
320 sterile Eppendorf and 200 µl of ddH₂O was added. After thorough grinding (Eppendorf), a
321 drop was visualized under a microscope to detect the presence of spores (Higes et al.,
322 2007). Afterwards, the 30 samples were mixed, homogenized, centrifuged and the spore
323 count obtained. The remaining homogenate was used for PCR analysis.

324 Molecular diagnosis was performed monthly to identify the species in all Nosema-positive
325 colonies. The analysis was performed in B255 from the 25 May 2005 to collapse on the 11
326 December 2006, and the nuclei were monitored monthly from June 2006 to April 2007.
327 Determinations in B111 started in June 2006 until collapse day on the 13 December 2007.
328 Infection was confirmed by PCR in all cases (Higes et al., 2006; Martín-Hernández et
329 al., 2007).

330 The identification of Nosema was carried out when a positive spore count was identified,
331 except for the treated nuclei where it was carried out monthly even when spores were not
332 identified. DNA was extracted from 500 µl of the remaining homogenate after
333 microscopy analysis of interior and foragers bees. Samples were shaken with ceramic
334 beads (MagNA Lyser Green Beads, Roche 03 358941 001) in MagNA Lyser (Roche) at 9500
335 r.p.m. for 95 s and the DNA extracted with MagNA Pure Compact Nucleic Acid Isolation
336 Kit I (Roche 03 730964 001) in a MagNA Pure Compact instrument (Roche). From May 2005
337 to June 2006, PCR was performed with NOS FOR/NOS REV primers, and the products were
338 subjected to SSUrRNA sequencing (Higes et al., 2006; 2007). More recent samples were
339 analysed by multiplex PCR (Martín-Hernández et al., 2007).

340

341 *Pathological studies*

342 Samples for pathological studies were taken from B255 and on dying bees collected from
343 the surrounding area. Two adult interior bees and two foragers were analysed monthly by
344 optical microscopy. After dissecting out the gut, the ventriculus was divided into sections,
345 fixed in 10% buffered formalin, embedded in paraffin wax, sectioned at 4 µm and stained
346 with haematoxylin and eosin. A complete histopathological study was performed in each
347 case. The ventriculus from another three interior and forager bees from colony B255 were
348 also analysed monthly in semithin (0.5 µm) and TEM studies (Higes et al., 2007).
349 Representative tissue areas for TEM analysis were selected after examining the semithin
350 sections. For thin and semi-thin sections, an Olympus BX 50 microscope with an Olympus
351 television camera was used connected to a Phillips 50× max Pentium computer with
352 micro Image Version 4.0 for Windows 98 image analysis software. The TEM images were

353 obtained and photographed with a Jeol 1010 electron microscope at an accelerating
354 voltage of 80–100 kV.

355

356 *Virological determinations*

357 Virus analysis was performed on interior and forager bees by Dr Ribiere (AFSSA) and Dr
358 Sela (University of Jerusalem) as described previously (Stoltz et al., 1995; Hung, 2000;
359 Benjeddou et al., 2001; Grabensteiner et al., 2001; Bakonyi et al., 2002; Blanchard et
360 al., 2007; Maori et al., 2007). The samples for virological analysis were collected from
361 the B255 colony in July 2006, October 2006 and December 2006 and on the day of colony
362 collapse. Samples from B111 were collected in October 2006, June 2007 and November
363 2007. Samples from untreated nuclei were collected on the day when each nucleus
364 collapsed. Samples from treated nuclei were also collected in April 2007, on the same day
365 when the last untreated nucleus collapsed. In the unmanaged control nuclei (NS1–NS4),
366 IAPV was only analysed when they collapsed.

367

368 *Palynological determinations*

369 To confirm the type of foraging crop and the nutritive availability of pollen in colonies (B255
370 and nuclei CN1–CN10), 0.5 g of stored pollen was diluted in 10 ml of acidulated H₂O
371 (0.5% H₂SO₄) and 1 ml was taken for pollen extraction (Erdtman, 1969). Species were
372 identified using a photographic atlas (Valdés et al., 1987; Faegri and Iversen, 1989) and
373 the reference collection of pollen slides from the CAR.

374

375 *Presence of pesticides*

376 Honey, pollen and bee samples from B255, and pollen samples from B111 and nuclei
377 were stored at –20°C in dark recipients until they were analysed. All samples were
378 subjected to a multi-residue analysis (Table S2) at the Chemical Laboratory (University
379 of Valladolid) following slight modifications of previously reported methods. Briefly, pollen
380 and bee samples were extracted with acetonitrile, water was added to the extract and the
381 mixture was subjected to solid-phase extraction on octadecyl silane cartridge (Jiménez et
382 al., 2007). Honey samples were diluted with methanol and solid-phase extraction on a
383 Florisil-packed column was performed (Jiménez et al., 1998). Finally, the analysis of
384 residues in the extracts was carried out by gas chromatography with mass spectrometric
385 detection in combination with a matrix-matched calibration.

386

387 *Meteorological data*

388 Meteorological data were obtained from the CREA-SIAR of the ‘Consejería de Agricultura
389 de la JCCM’ (http://crea.uclm.es/~siar/datmeteo/resu_hist.php). Monthly rainfall and
390 temperatures were recorded by standard procedures.

391

392 *Statistical analysis*

393 Pearson correlations (two-tailed, $P < 0.01$ level) were obtained to determine the
394 relationship between the percentage infection and the mean spore counts in forager and
395 interior bees, the brood combs, the combs with bees and the meteorological data in B255
396 colony. A principal components analysis for categorical data, CATPCA, was used to
397 determine the relationship between multiple parameters derived from measurements on
398 B255, and the variables were transformed with an optimal scaling process and
399 subsequently correlated. The relationships between the data are represented in a
400 component loading graph. A multiple linear regression analysis was performed in which
401 the choice of predictive variables was carried out automatically selecting the best-fit
402 model. The relationships were established between a criterion variable (frames full of
403 bees and brood combs) and a set of predictors (percentage infection of interior and
404 forager bees, temperatures and monthly rainfall). Statistical analyses were performed
405 using spss 15.0.1 and sas 9.1 for Windows XP.

406 To compare colonies from the second response trial, data were grouped as uninfected
407 colonies ($n = 17$), infected and treated ($n = 18$) and infected and untreated ($n = 15$) at the
408 moment the trial commenced. To study the dependence of these groups upon bee health,
409 the statistical analysis was cross-tabulated. Chi-squared tests ($P < 0.01$) and a
410 correspondence analysis were used to calculate the exact probabilities. To perform these
411 analyses, a variable related to bee health at the end of the trial was established with
412 different levels.

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414 **Acknowledgements**

415 We thank M. Ribière, F. Schurr and I. Sela for the virological analysis; F. A. Rojo Vázquez, N.
416 Azpiazu, A. Alonso, C. del Águila, L. Prieto and M. Spivak for reviewing the manuscript;
417 M.L. García and A. Fernández for image-processing. R.M-H. and A.V.G.-P. were co-
418 financed by the Junta de Comunidades de Castilla-La Mancha (JCCM) and INIA-European
419 Social Fund. The work reported here was supported by JCCM and Ministerio de
420 Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación (API/FEGA-MAPYA FOUNDS).

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543 **Figure 1.** Clinical monitoring of *N. ceranae* natural infection. A. Dynamics of natural *N.*
544 *ceranae* infection of a model colony and the phases of nosemosis. Percentage of *N.*
545 *ceranae*-infected bees (n = 30), mean spore count (n = 30) and number of combs
546 covered by brood or bees in the B255 colony. B. Dynamics of the natural infected *N.*
547 *ceranae* B111 colony and the phases of nosemosis. C. Colony collapse of untreated
548 colonies (B255, B111) and nuclei (CN1–CN5, NSN1–NSN4) could occur in the cold or
549 warm season. Boxplots display differences in the percentage of infection and spore
550 counts between dead bees collected when colonies collapsed during the warm (April
551 to May, n = 6) or cold (November to February, n = 5) months in the Spanish climatic
552 conditions. The horizontal line within each box marks the median. indicates collapse
553 of the colony. FB, forager bees; IB, interior bees.

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563 **Figure 2.** Experiment 1: response trials with Fumidil B treatment in natural *N. ceranae*-
 564 infected nuclei. Mean dynamics of brood combs and bee combs, and the mean
 565 percentage infection of interior bees (n = 30) and foragers (n = 30) in (A) untreated (n = 5)
 566 and (B) fumagillin-treated (n = 5) nuclei (error bars as mean \pm SD). Shaded areas indicate
 567 the moment of application (fumagillin in treated nuclei and syrup in untreated ones). inline
 568 image indicates collapse of the untreated colonies.

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587 **Figure 3.** Microscopy images of an infected bee ventriculus and *N. ceranae* stages.
588 A. Representative example of infected epithelial cells filled with different stage parasites.
589 A predominance of basophilic mature spores in the apical cytoplasm is seen, the bottom
590 of the cytoplasm is full of more vegetative parasites (MS, mature spore; N, nucleus; IS,
591 immature stage; V, vacuole). Toluidine blue staining (20× magnification).
592 B. Infected epithelial cells with breakage of the cell plasma membrane at the base of the
593 brush border. Brightly stained nucleus displaced apically and vacuolar basal degeneration
594 were evident in the enlarged parasitized cells (4000× magnification).
595 C. Detail of an extruded spore inside an infected cell indicating that intracellular
596 germination of spores takes place (60 000× magnification).

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600 **Figure 4.** Diagram summarizing the distribution and location of colonies and nuclei
 601 between the different apiaries, the time course of sampling and infection status of *N.*
 602 *ceranae*.

*5 of this colonies were used as control in Experiment 1

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608 **Table 1.** Characteristics of colony breakdown in the cold or warm season.

Colony	Brood cells	Bees	% Infection on worker bees	<i>N. ceranae</i> (spores/bee) Worker bees (mean)	Queen
Cold season breakdown					
B255	100	133	50	12.75×10^6	0.2×10^6
B111	241	231	51	10.8×10^6	0.1×10^6
CN6	50	13	90	21×10^6	0.21×10^6
CN9	250	33	65	25×10^6	Not found
CN10	350	65	50	11.9×10^6	0.4×10^6
Warm season breakdown					
CN7	0	350	44	1.1×10^6	< 50 000 (PCR+)
CN8	400	150	30	1×10^6	Negative
NSN1	200	350	15	0.25×10^6	< 50 000 (PCR+)
NSN2	1200	1081	35	3.5×10^6	Negative
NSN3	500	512	30	2×10^6	Negative
NSN4	0	0	Not found	Not found	Not found

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610 Cold season breakdown from December to February; warm season breakdown from April
 611 to June. B255 and B111 hives and CN6–CN10 nuclei were treated and sampled monthly,
 612 while NSN1–NSN4 were nuclei not treated and not sampled till they were dead.

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620 **Table 2.** Samples from untreated nuclei were taken on the collapse date and samples
 621 from the treated ones were collected when the last untreated nuclei collapsed (April
 622 2007).

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Colony	CBPV ^a	ABPV	DWV	SBV	KBV	BQCV	IAPV
CN1	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
CN2	ND	ND	Positive	ND	ND	ND	ND
CN3	Positive 7.26 × 10 ⁶	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
CN4	Positive 2.01 × 10 ⁷	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
CN5	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
CN6	Positive 6.05 × 10 ⁶	ND	Positive	ND	ND	Positive	ND
CN7	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
CN8	ND	ND	Positive	ND	ND	ND	ND
CN9	ND	ND	Positive	ND	ND	ND	ND
CN10	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
B255							
July 2006	Positive	ND	Positive	ND	ND	ND	ND
October 2006	Positive 2.29 × 10 ⁵	ND	Positive	ND	ND	ND	ND
December 2006	Positive 6.05 × 10 ⁶	ND	Positive	ND	ND	ND	ND
B111							
October 2006	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
June 2007	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
November 2007	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
Colony	NSN1	NSN2	NSN3	NSN4			
IAPV	ND	Positive	ND	ND			

624 a. Quantitatively analysed. Samples were taken from B255 and B111 at different times.
 625 ND, not detected; KBV, Kashmir bee virus; SBV, sacbrood virus; ABPV, acute bee paralysis
 626 virus; BQCV, black queen cell virus.

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629 **Table 3.** Experiment 2: colony response trial.

Group	n	Intervention	Colonies positives to <i>N. ceranae</i> or death				Nosemosis status 11.11.07
			30.10.06 ^a	15.12.06	26.04.07	26.09.07	
Positive treated	18	Fumagillin (120 mg)	18	0	5	18	18 in Phase 1
Positive untreated	15	Syrup	15	13 ^b 2 death	6 7 death ^c	2 4 death ^c	1 in Phase 2 1 in Phase 4
Negative untreated	17	Syrup	0	5	17	14	4 in Phase 2 5 death

630 a. Pre-treatment. b. Two colonies infected by *N. ceranae* and *N. apis*. c. One colony
 631 infected by *N. ceranae* and *N. apis*. 0 13b 2 death 5 5 6 7 deathc 17 18 2 4 deathc 14
 632 Nosemosis status 11.11.07 18 in Phase 1 1 in Phase 2 1 in Phase 4 4 in Phase 2 5 death
 633 Treatments (fumagillin as Fumidil· B in treated colonies and syrup in non-treated ones)
 634 were applied as described in the Experimental procedures. The first sampling of apiaries
 635 was made on the 30 October 2006, a day before the application of treatment. Nosemosis
 636 status represents the number of colonies according to the phases described in Fig. 1